

USING BIG DATA TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF A SMART CAMPUS

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Abstract. This article presents the Big Data technologies used in the development of a smart campus. In the field of education, there are five types of big data for analysis: personal data; data on student learning: electronic textbooks, online courses, page views, the number of refusals to read; data on the use of educational materials: administrative data: attendance, absences due to illness; forecasts of student participation in certain activities of the university. The concept of a Smart Campus is defined and an example is given. Several areas are listed that are relied on when developing a smart campus.

Keywords: *big data technology, motivation to study, «Smart» campus- concept, electronic attendance system, Q-NEX Smart campus solution.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Electronic systems of universities store arrays of information about the educational process. Information about students' academic performance and attendance, educational and administrative activities of teachers, materials for training - entire archives. In order to process them, analyze them, and direct the conclusions to improve educational processes, they use Big Data technology. Big Data is one of the main innovative trends implemented in a variety of areas from economics to medicine, which integrates the analysis of large information flows using machine learning, allowing you to make accurate forecasts, determine the

target audience, establish cause-and-effect relationships of phenomena and much more. In the structure and development of universities, the conclusions made using this approach help to track the dynamics and priorities of the processes taking place in the university, structure the educational space and establish its functioning, build a long-term development policy. The effectiveness of this approach is noticeable in a variety of details related to student everyday life. To collect information for further analysis, the university is filled with various sensors, video cameras, united into one high-speed network. But the sources of data are not limited to these devices. An important resource of information are the students and teachers themselves, because now almost every person owns a smartphone, which provides real-time data on movement, courses, subjects and preferences [1,2].

II. METHODS

What Big Data Can Do. In the education sector, there are five types of big data for analysis: personal data; data on student learning: what electronic textbooks, online courses, page views, number of refusals to read; data on the use of educational materials: what content students choose to prepare for classes; administrative data: attendance, absences due to illness; forecasts of student participation in certain university activities. Thanks to the ability to generalize and operate large volumes of information, Big Data technology helps make the educational process more interesting [3].

Analysis of the experience of teachers and students will suggest a suitable teaching method. This will be the result of mass practical application, and not the experience of one or several specialists. Analytics data can influence changes in the program of educational courses and the creation of a curriculum that will include only those methods whose effectiveness has been proven by results. Only what is interesting and useful to students [4].

The processed data shows what type of student uses what content for learning, what educational materials he is interested in, which he refuses, how a particular course is going, where he turns for help. In the future, such analysis will help to select an individual training program for each student, to create personal homework. The technology helps to identify lagging students and guide them in choosing a direction that best suits their personal qualities and abilities. Technologies used for big data: 1. Collection. Big data is collected from different sources. 2. Storage. Regular data is placed on one computer or online disk. This is not possible with big data, so it is stored and processed using cloud servers and distributed computing power. Thanks to this, several people can work with Big Data at the same time, accessing it from different points. 3. Processing. It will be difficult to process large

amounts of information using regular tools: it will take too much time. For these tasks, special software is used that works using MapReduce technology. First, the algorithm selects data according to specified parameters, then distributes it between separate nodes, servers or computers, and then they simultaneously process these data segments, in parallel with each other. 4. Analysis. To use big data in work, it is necessary to analyze it by a variety of parameters. This is helped by: SQL - a query language that is used when working with relational DBMS. Neural networks trained using machine learning to process tons of information in seconds and provide accurate data for the most complex tasks [5].

Motivation to study. In Western educational practice, Big Data technology is used to motivate students to study. Nottingham Trent University has installed a student performance monitoring panel. The monitor displays each student's academic performance in comparison with their classmates: attendance, frequency of work with the library, courses studied. Each student sees their own activity, compares themselves with others in order to understand how involved they are in their studies and university life, where they are lagging behind or not showing themselves enough. If a student is inactive for two weeks, the platform signals this to the course curator so that he can support the student, and help if necessary. After three years of the system's operation, 72% of first-year students note that student monitoring motivates them to devote more time to their studies.

At Austin Peay University, Big Data technology is used to recommend a course to a student so that it matches their interests, abilities, and curriculum. To do this, the system analyzes the results of previous students in the course, academic performance, and information about students with similar interests. The accuracy of recommendations for a suitable course is 90%.

Big Data technology provides teachers with timely information about students' academic performance, helps monitor learning, modify curricula so that they are more useful and interesting for students, and recommends suitable courses to students. The practice of using scientific achievements is expanding, and the agenda includes the presentation of updated university campuses: automated, technological, modern [6].

"Smart" campus - concept

A modern university is akin to an entire city with its dormitories, libraries, concert halls, hospitals, sports complexes, canteens and cafes. Such a university, "integrated" into the urban environment with its streets, roads and garages, becomes a full-fledged student town. There are already enough examples of such student towns in Russia. One of the most striking is Akademgorodok in Novosibirsk, a scientific, administrative and educational center located in the middle of the forest.

And yet, for a long time, independently functioning university towns were not fully automated, and developed infrastructure sometimes grew around the university chaotically and unpredictably, like mushroom caps appearing in the grass in rainy autumn.

The rethought concept of a university, all systems and departments of which function as a single organism with due technological control, turned into the idea of a "smart" campus. "Smart campus" are themes that have been gaining momentum in the higher education sector for the past few years. There is great potential and opportunity for property and facilities managers, but it also comes with its own set of challenges [7,8].

Campus facilities managers face a multitude of issues, many of which are related to digitalization, economics, changing demographics, and innovations in educational models. And of course, one of the overarching challenges is ensuring an optimal campus eco-environment at an effective cost for students, staff, and faculty. Higher education institutions are using a variety of innovative technologies and software solutions to try to find ways to plan and execute campus operations more efficiently. But when is a campus considered "smart"?

What is a Smart Campus

Traditionally, a "campus" for a higher education institution has been defined as "the buildings and land shared for university or university-related functions." However, many universities today are working to deliver something more – a campus that sets them apart from others and provides stakeholders with a connected, modern experience. There is a more holistic approach to managing not only the physical infrastructure, but also the learning infrastructure and digital infrastructure of the campus. This combination of managing the physical and digital infrastructure together is the element that begins to point to a smart campus.

III. RESULTS

Innovations on the way to university transformation. What should a university campus be like to be classified as "smart"? Most likely, various technological innovations in education, access to digital space and robotic technology to simplify life come to mind. Of course, all this characterizes the next generation of universities. However, in the construction of new-format campuses, an important role is also played by the harmonious combination of man-made and natural, as well as the use of environmentally friendly materials with care for the future.

Often, such universities are designed with an initial focus on creating a comfortable living environment, and therefore recreation areas are included in the construction plans [9-11].

Fig. 1. Example of a "Smart" campus

Several areas are highlighted that are relied upon when developing a "smart" campus. 1. Greening and comfortable environment. We have already noted above that a "smart" campus implies not only a technically equipped space, but also a comfortable one that compensates for the harm to nature and reduces the level of stress associated with life in a metropolis. This solution is the creation of parks, green areas or integrating the campus into the natural environment with its relief, forest and water surfaces.

2. Materials and technologies. An important trend in modern "smart" construction is the use of environmentally friendly materials and energy-saving technologies. Starting from the use of energy-efficient LED and fluorescent lamps in classrooms, sensor faucets in restrooms and ending with the use of more economical materials during cosmetic repairs. Campus maps. It is assumed that such a card can combine the functions of a pass, an identity card, an electronic library card and a bank card for paying for services and goods from stores inside the campus. When implementing such an idea, even an internal currency can be introduced, allowing the campus to exist in a closed cycle (however, the issue of introducing such technologies is highly debatable) [12-14].

3. Electronic attendance system. In many universities in Russia, this idea is no longer innovative: electronic passes recording attendance have become a part of our lives. For a "smart" campus, this is already a mandatory, integral element of a comfortable environment for all participants in the educational process.

4. Campus information portals. A single digital system in which you can find out your schedule, pay for dormitory accommodation, see the bus route around the

campus, ask the rector a question - this is what the creators of new-format campuses are striving for.

5. Gamification and digitalization in education. Digitalization is part of our reality. Education in the difficult realities of this year has proven the need to create and improve a system of remote access to educational materials, create online university courses and more. Another part of this large-scale process is gamification, which is successfully used as a tool for motivating learning. What is meant by gamification in this case? For example, get special stickers for a month without absenteeism or win a coupon for a free lunch for all the first classes this semester that you attended - and all this in a special game program on your smartphone.

6. Multimedia studios. Modernization will also affect the interior decoration of university premises, where it is planned to place multimedia studios. Their purpose is not limited to cinemas and libraries, this is a modern space for the development of creativity, blogging, journalistic endeavors, for working on design projects.

7. Dronedromes. Even roofs are planned to be used effectively. Equipped with solar panels, landing pads for drones and — for them — charging stations, such roofs will help optimize space and save space on the streets, opening up new opportunities for information exchange, cargo transportation and more.

8. Autodrome for unmanned vehicles. Another innovation that is planned to be used in the “smart” campus is an unmanned vehicle for comfortable movement between campus buildings [15-17].

9. Wind-solar power plants. Finally, another achievement of human technical thought, as well as a way to produce energy in an environmentally friendly and efficient manner - wind-solar power plants. Installed in accordance with the needs of campus residents, such solar panels and power plants will be able to provide them with sufficient energy.

Examples of "smart" campuses

Perhaps some of the above-mentioned tools and guidelines used to create a "smart" campus seem unattainable and futuristic, especially in Russian realities.

Abroad, modern university campuses are appearing more and more often: examples include universities in Chicago and Singapore. Projects to create such campuses have been discussed for about ten years, and some of them have already been implemented, although not on the scale expected. Since 2013, a university student campus has been operating on Russky Island. Now there are educational and sports buildings, dormitories-hotels, sports grounds, a park, an embankment, cafes and canteens, and an internal pass system is used.

For example, let's assume that a place in the classroom is booked in advance for a certain course for 300 students every Monday at 9:00 throughout the academic year. If in the third week, an hour before a class, a bad weather warning is issued, an

automatic change to the booked classroom can be made, since based on the analysis of scheduling data, previous usage and attendance, weather, traffic and student behavior, it can be reasonably predicted that around 120 students will attend this lecture. The immediate scheduling change is automatically processed in the relevant systems and communicated to all stakeholders. This change immediately contributes to efficient use of space, cost effectiveness and student and staff satisfaction. This is just one small example of the huge potential of a smart campus. If campus managers are able to identify the right business case and use cases, and implement the right smart campus technology, they can really reap the benefits and improve staff and faculty productivity, and achieve significant cost savings [18-20].

IV. DISCUSSION

Smart campuses are a fast-growing trend that is revolutionizing the way we live and work. The concept is simple: you can use technology to make your campus more efficient and productive. In this article, we will show you how you can create a smart campus by integrating AV control systems with Q-NEX Solutions.

Fig.2. Q-NEX Smart Campus Solution

Fig. 3. Location of connected devices

V. CONCLUSION

Q-NEX solutions are a comprehensive suite of products designed to help you build a smart campus. The AV control system automatically adjusts lighting, temperature, and humidity settings to keep your building comfortable and energy efficient. It also provides centralized control of all your AV equipment, so it's easy to set up and shut down. With Q-NEX solutions, you can: Increase employee productivity by ensuring they're working in the most comfortable conditions. Reduce energy consumption by lowering the temperature and turning off the lights when no one is home. You need a smart campus solution to manage your campus. We have the most advanced AV control system available, and our efficiency is second to none. Our centralized control allows you to easily monitor everything that's happening in your school or office – from student IDs to access permissions.

We can also set up a system to broadcast important announcements and instructions so everyone in your building knows what's going on at a glance. With Q-NEX, you'll never have to worry about losing control of any aspect of your campus again. Q-NEX solutions can provide you with an AV management system that can automatically broadcast information to all devices on campus, including webcams, projectors, and more. This ensures that all students, faculty, and staff are aware of important events such as fires or other emergencies. It also provides centralized management of your entire campus so that you can easily coordinate maintenance efforts. The goals of the "Smart Campus" project are: accessibility of

learning in an interactive environment; individual approach and conditions for each university student; easy access to university resources and other foreign universities.

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